

PEDAGOGIC PRACTICES OF SOCIAL SCIENCE TEACHERS

M. Papaiah,

Lecturer Telangana

Dr. Shahanaz Begum,

Associate Professor (Retd), University College of Education, Osmania University,

Hyderabad, Telangana

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Abstract

Pedagogy is a system and process of tutoring in which preceptors educate both in proposition and in practice. Pedagogy is shaped by learners tutoring beliefs and involves their understanding of culture and different literacy styles. Pedagogic practices are means by which literacy guests can be amended to promote scholars' literacy veritably creative. Pedagogy refers to the way of tutoring scholars, whether it's the proposition or practice of educating. It's a relationship between the culture and ways of literacy. The present abstract exploration concentrated on Pedagogic practices of Social Science preceptors. The main end of pedagogy is to make on former literacy of the scholars and work on the development of chops and stations of the learners. Pedagogy enables the scholars to get a thorough understanding of the subject and helps them in applying those learning in their diurnal lives outside of the classroom.

Pedagogy in teaching can be referred to as an educator's understanding of how the students learn. The teachers are focused on presenting the syllabus to the students in such a way that it is relevant to their needs. Pedagogy demands classroom interactions between the teacher and students which create a significant impact on the learner's mind.

Pedagogy enables teachers to understand the best suitable practices for a classroom setting. It helps them to know how different students learn and grasp information so that they can tailor their lessons to satisfy those needs. It is likely to improve the quality of teaching and the way it is received by the students. The present paper focused on Pedagogic practices of Social Science Teachers with prime objectives are- (i) To understand the concept of Pedagogic practices. (ii) To analyse the importance of Pedagogic practices of Social Science Teachers. (iii) To discuss the strategies of Pedagogic practices for Social Science Teachers. The technique of the inquire about could be a sort including an interpretative, discussion, perception and consider auxiliary sources, like books, articles, diaries, proposal, college news, master supposition, and websites, etc.

Key Words: *Pedagogic practices, Social Science Teachers*

Introduction: The conception of pedagogic practices encompasses the styles, strategies, ways, and approaches that preceptors use to grease literacy and promote the intellectual, social, and

emotional development of learners. Pedagogic practices are deeply embedded in educational proposition and exploration and are informed by the principles of tutoring and literacy. Then are some crucial aspects of the conception of pedagogic practices-

Concept of Pedagogic Practices: Pedagogy enables preceptors to understand the stylish suitable practices for a classroom setting. It helps them to know how different scholars learn and grasp information so that they can conform their assignments to satisfy those requirements. It's likely to ameliorate the quality of tutoring and the way it's entered by the scholars.

Pedagogy plays an important part to help preceptors understand the stylish ways to conduct a classroom. It gives them perceptivity into how scholars learn else in different motifs so that they can conduct assignments to suit these requirements. It aims to ameliorate the quality of education for scholars.

Learning proposition: Pedagogic practices are predicated in colourful literacy propositions that seek to understand how literacy occurs and how preceptors can best grease it. These propositions include behaviourism, cognitivism, constructivism, social literacy proposition, and socio-artistic proposition, among others. Pedagogic practices are shaped by the principles and perceptivity of these propositions, guiding preceptors in designing effective educational strategies.

Student-Centered Approach: Pedagogic practices emphasize the significance of placing scholars at the centre of the literacy process. This involves feting scholars as active actors in their own literacy and acclimatizing instruction to meet their individual requirements, interests, and capacities. Student- centered pedagogy encourages autonomy, critical thinking, and engagement, fostering deeper understanding and long- term retention of knowledge.

Active Learning: Pedagogic practices promote active engagement and participation in the literacy process. rather of passively entering information, scholars are encouraged to laboriously construct their understanding through hands- on conditioning, conversations, problem- working tasks, and cooperative systems. Active literacy fosters deeper appreciation, advanced- order thinking chops, and a sense of power over learning issues.

Differentiation: Pedagogic practices fete the diversity of learners and seek to accommodate their varied requirements, preferences, and capacities. Preceptor's separate instruction by conforming tutoring styles, accoutrements, and assessments to meet the individual literacy styles, readiness situations, and interests of scholars. This ensures that all scholars have indifferent openings to succeed and reach their full eventuality.

Reflection and Feedback: Pedagogic practices emphasize the significance of ongoing reflection and feedback to support pupil literacy and growth. preceptors encourage scholars to reflect on their literacy gests, set pretensions, and cover their progress over time. preceptors give formative feedback that helps scholars identify strengths and areas for enhancement, guiding them toward mastery and tone- directed literacy.

Inquiry and Problem-Based Learning: Pedagogic practices promote inquiry-based and problem-based approaches to learning, where students actively explore questions, issues, and challenges, and develop solutions through investigation and analysis. These approaches cultivate curiosity, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills, preparing students to navigate complex real-world problems and make informed decisions.

Pedagogic practices and Social Science Teacher: Social science teachers play a crucial role in educating students about various aspects of human society, including history, geography, economics, political science, sociology, and anthropology. Their responsibilities extend beyond simply delivering content; they also help students develop critical thinking skills, cultivate an understanding of complex social issues, and foster a sense of civic responsibility. Here are some key aspects of the role of social science teachers:

Content Delivery: Social science teachers are responsible for delivering curriculum content in their respective fields, covering topics such as historical events, geographic features, economic

systems, political structures, cultural practices, and societal trends. They must possess a strong understanding of their subject matter and stay updated on developments in their fields.

Curriculum Development: In addition to teaching existing curriculum standards, social science teachers often contribute to the development of curriculum materials, including lesson plans, instructional resources, and assessments. They may collaborate with colleagues to align curriculum content with educational standards and ensure coherence across grade levels.

Instructional Planning: Social science teachers carefully plan instructional activities to engage students and promote learning. This may involve designing lessons that incorporate a variety of teaching strategies, such as lectures, discussions, group work, multimedia presentations, and hands-on activities.

Classroom Management: Effective classroom management is essential for creating a positive and productive learning environment. Social science teachers establish clear expectations for behaviour, manage classroom routines effectively, and address disciplinary issues in a fair and consistent manner.

Facilitation of Inquiry and Critical Thinking: Social science teachers encourage students to ask questions, think critically, and analyse evidence to develop a deeper understanding of social phenomena. They facilitate classroom discussions, guide students in conducting research, and help them evaluate sources of information.

Cultural Competence and Inclusivity: Social science teachers strive to create inclusive classrooms where students from diverse backgrounds feel valued and respected. They incorporate diverse perspectives into their teaching, address sensitive topics with sensitivity and empathy, and foster an appreciation for cultural diversity.

Professional Development: Social science teachers engage in ongoing professional development to stay current with best practices in teaching and learning. This may involve attending workshops, conferences, and professional development seminars, pursuing advanced degrees or certifications, and collaborating with colleagues to share expertise and resources.

Community Engagement: Social science teachers often seek opportunities to connect classroom learning to real-world contexts through community engagement activities such as service-learning projects, guest speakers, field trips, and partnerships with local organizations and institutions.

Overall, social science teachers play a vital role in preparing students to become informed and engaged citizens who understand the complexities of the world around them and are equipped to contribute positively to society.

Innovative Pedagogic Practices for Social Science Subject: The pedagogic practices of social science teachers can vary widely depending on factors such as educational philosophy, teaching style, student demographics, and institutional context. However, there are several common pedagogical approaches and strategies that many social science teachers employ-

Inquiry-Based Learning: Social science teachers often utilize inquiry-based learning approaches, where students are encouraged to ask questions, investigate issues, and analyse evidence to construct their understanding of key concepts. This approach fosters critical thinking skills and encourages students to actively engage with the material.

Experiential Learning: Teachers may incorporate experiential learning activities such as simulations, role-plays, case studies, and field trips to help students connect theoretical concepts to real-world situations. Experiential learning can deepen students' understanding of social phenomena and enhance their empathy and perspective-taking abilities.

Discussion-Based Instruction: Social science classrooms are often characterized by lively discussions where students are encouraged to express their opinions, engage in respectful debate, and critically evaluate different perspectives. Teachers facilitate these discussions by asking thought-provoking questions, providing scaffolding when necessary, and creating a supportive learning environment.

Multimedia Resources: With advancements in technology, social science teachers frequently incorporate multimedia resources such as videos, podcasts, interactive websites, and online databases to supplement traditional instructional materials. These resources can help make abstract concepts more concrete, cater to different learning styles, and enhance student engagement.

Primary Source Analysis: Analysing primary sources such as historical documents, speeches, diaries, and artifacts is a fundamental aspect of social science education. Teachers guide students through the process of critically examining primary sources, considering their context, bias, and reliability, and using them to construct historical narratives or support arguments.

Project-Based Learning: Social science teachers may design project-based learning experiences where students work collaboratively to investigate complex issues, conduct research, and present their findings to authentic audiences. Projects can range from designing community action plans to creating multimedia presentations on global issues, allowing students to develop research, communication, and teamwork skills.

Differentiated Instruction: Recognizing the diverse needs and abilities of students, social science teachers employ differentiated instruction strategies to accommodate various learning

styles, interests, and proficiency levels. This may involve providing alternative assessments, offering flexible grouping arrangements, and adapting instructional materials to meet individual student needs.

Critical Media Literacy: In an age of pervasive media consumption, social science teachers often incorporate lessons on critical media literacy, helping students analyse and evaluate media messages, recognize bias and misinformation, and understand the social, economic, and political implications of media representations.

Culturally Relevant Pedagogy: Effective social science teaching involves acknowledging and valuing students' diverse cultural backgrounds and lived experiences. Teachers may incorporate culturally relevant pedagogy by selecting instructional materials that reflect diverse perspectives, incorporating culturally responsive teaching practices, and fostering inclusive classroom environments where all students feel respected and represented.

Formative Assessment and Feedback: Social science teachers use formative assessment techniques such as quizzes, discussions, written reflections, and peer review to monitor student progress, identify misconceptions, and provide timely feedback for improvement. By assessing student learning throughout the instructional process, teachers can adjust their teaching strategies to better meet students' needs and promote deeper understanding.

Conclusion: Overall, effective social science pedagogy emphasizes active student engagement, critical thinking, inquiry, and the development of essential skills for civic participation and informed citizenship.

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